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**THE POST-WAR STATE OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF
KARAKALPAKSTAN'S ECONOMY**

Annotation: In the article, the post-war state of the agricultural sector of the economy of Karakalpakstan, the selfless work of the people of Karakalpakstan in 1945, and the agricultural sector are also described.

Key words: economy, in rural areas, animal husbandry, sericulture, vegetables.

After the Second World War, the agriculture of Karakalpakstan faced many difficulties. The war made the agricultural situation difficult, and as the arable land decreased, the cultivation of the fields worsened. At the same time, due to the war, the working population has decreased by almost one-third percent. If in 1940, the number of the rural population of the republic was 423 thousand people (at that time the total population of the republic was 488 thousand people), in the post-war period their number decreased significantly. The number of rural population in 1950, that is, 417.9 thousand people lived in the rural areas of Karakalpakstan, this indicator reached the pre-war level.

At the end of the war, i.e. in 1945, selfless work of the people of Karakalpakstan was clearly not enough to fulfill the plan of production of agricultural products. For example, in 1945, only the laborers of Tortkol and Khojayli regions were able to fulfill the plan to prepare raw cotton and transfer it to the state, while other regions of the republic remained in debt to the state. The yield of cotton grown in the fields did not exceed 9.7 centners per hectare. There are many reasons for such crisis situations in agriculture, including the fact that the farms mainly use manual labor, there are no processing mechanisms, and the state of irrigation systems did not meet the requirements of that time. Prof. K. Sarybaev said that the lack of water distribution facilities and devices led to uneven distribution of water resources: in some places, water was used excessively, and there were frequent cases where water did not even reach remote areas. It was in 1945 that water did not reach the remote farming areas, and since the tractors necessary for planting crops were not available until the 1950s, cattle, horses and donkeys had to be used for heavy work.

Since the agriculture of Karakalpakstan was considered the basis of the economy of the republic, all production was concentrated in agricultural collective farms. It is known that due to the policy of the Soviet state, collective farmers did not have any rights as a result of not being issued passports. The work of the disenfranchised people who worked in collective farms, who had neither the opportunity to leave the collective farm nor to change their place of residence, was almost free, and they did not even have the guarantee of social protection. This situation made it possible to provide the state with agricultural raw materials and other products for a certain period under the conditions of a strong administrative system. In agricultural production, they specialized in growing not only cotton, but also rice, alfalfa seeds, cow hides, wool, and silkworms. Agriculture of the republic was mainly based on artificial irrigation. As soon as the war ended, Soviet party organizations first began to develop a plan to increase agricultural production in 1946. For example, according to the plan of 1946, it was necessary to increase the raw material of cotton to 12 centners per hectare. It was also decided to increase

the planting of wheat and millet to 3,700 hectares, to increase the yield of wheat to 10.1 quintals per hectare, and of millet to 6 quintals per hectare. The plan also emphasized the need for mechanization of agricultural production. 54,000 hectares were allocated for cotton planting, and in this case, it was planned to increase the size of cultivated land in the republic to 154,800 hectares. Alfalfa, corn, sesame, and other technical crops were also cultivated. In addition, the land allocated for livestock and silk farming was also somewhat expanded.

68 percent of the state budget approved in 1946 in the amount of 105,838 thousand rubles was directed to the social and cultural sphere, and approximately 14 percent (14,598 thousand rubles) was directed to the development of agriculture, water management, road construction, forestry and the improvement of communal facilities. The Central Committee of the Communist Party of the All-Union (Bolsheviks) and the Central Committee of the USSR dated February 2, 1946 "On the plan and measures for the restoration and further development of cotton production in Uzbekistan in the period 1946-1953" set the cotton production plan in Karakalpakstan in 1947 as 100,000 tons, by 1950 and this indicator should be brought up to 168 tons, according to the plan, the yield from one hectare to 11.5 centners of cotton raw material should be obtained. In the decisions of the government of the republic, special attention was paid to other areas of agriculture, including animal husbandry, sericulture, cultivation of vegetable crops, and it was shown the necessity of production of agricultural products due to the expansion of cultivated areas. For example, the number of horned cattle in the republic decreased to a certain extent during the war years. Even in 1945, the number of horned cattle decreased by 9-11% in Kipchak, Takhtako'prik, Kuybyshev regions. This situation was also mentioned at the Republican meeting of advanced cattle breeders in the city of Nukus (March 19-20, 1946). By the decision of the government, instead of 475 collective farms, 38 collective farms and 20 large state farms were established in the northern regions of Karakalpakstan. caused damage in the amount of rubles. Organized chaos and instability began in the districts, and the positive qualities of the implemented reforms changed their form in many ways.

In 1959-1965, 1,558,000 tons of cotton were produced in the republic, and in 1963, this figure reached 135.4 hectares, 15.8 centners of product were obtained from each hectare. 7500 hectares of new land was acquired for rice cultivation in 1962-1965. Expansion of new lands was primarily directed to cotton cultivation and the development of this sector, while such branches of agriculture as vegetable cultivation, horticulture and viticulture could not develop sufficiently. In the 1960s, the share of land for vegetable cultivation and potato cultivation occupied only 1.3% of the total of the republic, and the cultivated products were not even enough to meet domestic needs. Thus, great attention was paid to the expansion of cultivated areas, the development of previously vacant lands, irrigation facilities and canals were built or renovated in many districts. However, despite attempts to carry out reforms in the agricultural sector, the establishment of a cotton monopoly, the unsatisfactory state of the material and technical base in the conditions of the autonomous republic in 1959-1965 showed its negative results.

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